

An inquiry into Fab Labs as enablers for environmental protection initiatives

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Abstract

Fab Labs are small-scale workshops offering digital fabrication at different scales. These spaces are known for fostering learning in technological and manufacturing skills as well as offering services, with a collaborative mindset. In this paper, we explore an unexplored growing trend within Fab Labs: their involvement in participatory approaches and their thematic focus on environmentally related activities. Although recent research has highlighted their increasing focus on sustainability aspects of their activities, such as investigation connected to lifecycle assessment analysis and environmental impact of selected machinery, their role in cultivating environmentally conscious communities and catalyzing collaborative practices such as citizen science in environmental initiatives warrants further exploration. This paper investigates the capacity of Fab Labs as enablers of environmental protection in collaboration with citizen science initiatives, and other key actors, such as environmental agencies, NGOs and local government, by collecting data on those cases via literature review and interviews, and analyzing real-world cases from the global Fab Lab Network. The work aims to highlight the potential of Fab Labs as enablers for environmental action and, by showcasing inspiring initiatives, we aspire to enhance the recognition of Fab Labs as environments for citizen-driven environmental protection efforts, fostering broader participation and impactful change.

Keywords

Environmental protection, enablers, community engagement, citizen science

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Fab Labs are commonly regarded as digital fabrication spaces whose activities typically relate to training on digital skills, manufacturing and prototyping services, as well as technology and design consultancy. However, many Fab Labs have developed activities that go beyond their initially envisioned purposes as explored by various authors (Boeva, Y. 2018; Durán–López, E. C., 2022; Millet, E. J. 2021; Paeva, V., 2023), developing relationships with local stakeholders and participating in activities that seemingly do not pertain to these manufacturing spaces. In addition, the Fab Lab collaborative mindset and a commitment to being open to the local communities (Center for Bits and Atoms, MIT, 2012) can favor these relationships, which could strengthen Fab Labs' potential to develop more complex links in which they can play a pivotal role in multi stakeholder processes.

This study focuses on a particular field of activities which have links to environmentally related topics in various forms such as environmental protection, awareness raising campaigns, community action and environmental monitoring. The involvement of Fab Labs in this particular field of activities is generally unexplored in the literature and, given the lack of documentation on the topic, this paper aims to provide a first attempt to collate these activities in a systematic way and understand how the Fab Labs interviewed have developed these roles and relationships with environmentally active communities and groups. In particular, we focus on what type of activities they are involved in, which stakeholders are involved in those activities, how those relationships came about, and what were the main motivations and barriers in those processes. This paper also aims to build upon existing theoretical frameworks for understanding these relationships, and delves into potential ways in which these collaborations can be fostered in the future.

1.2 Background

This research paper is part of the more4nature project. more4nature is an European-funded project (Grant agreement ID: 101133983) that aims to trigger transformative change in environmental protection and conservation efforts in three thematic areas: zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention. The project valorizes the pivotal role that citizens and communities play in these processes, and aims to strengthen their role in environmental compliance. Using more4nature as a platform, this research paper analyzes the potential roles of Fab Labs as key enablers in environmental protection initiatives.

In this analysis, we focus on the particular role that Fab Labs can take on in collaboration with other stakeholders in relation to what could be generally referred to as “environmentalism.” As such, we consider the term to refer to “concern for the environment and particularly actions or advocacy to limit negative human impacts on the environment” (Davies, 2020). We acknowledge that the choice for the umbrella term of “environmentalism” can be controversial, as “this broad brush understanding masks a plethora of diverse ethics, politics, and views of how the world is and how it ought to be.” However, we consider that more theoretical discussion to be out of the scope of our analysis as we believe that the concept of environmentalism, in its generally accepted sense, can be properly linked to the type of analysis that we are conducting as part of our paper.

The role of the Fab Labs in environmental related projects (including those closer to citizen science) is presented in this paper based on some items drawn from the Janus framework (Liñán et al., 2022), which aims to provide a theoretical framework for community engagement in citizen science projects, generally in environmental monitoring activities. Based on their work, we introduce some conceptual adaptations due to the broader scope of the activities that Fab Labs are involved in (i.e. not just monitoring), and we also include adaptations in what the drivers for Fab Labs are in order to take part in these initiatives. In their paper, authors of the Janus framework introduce the concept of “enablers”, which are stakeholders from the core subsystems in the Quintuple innovation helix framework (academia, industry, government) (Peris-Ortiz et al., 2016). The role of these “enablers” is to help overcome the wide variety of barriers that can take place in the activities that stakeholders are involved in, as well as within the interactions between them in citizen science projects, by generating triggers and motivating inputs, increasing the community’s or stakeholders’ abilities, and generating rewards for participants. However, given that the different stakeholders and communities that are involved in these projects have different temporal requirements with regards to those barriers, triggers and expectations (i.e. the creation of scientific outputs, or the implementation of policy is a long-term process, which can conflict with the short-term expectations of citizens and communities), the model considers that these “enablers” play a pivotal role in these relationships, because they accommodate for those temporal (and other) asymmetries, facilitating the conversations, and ultimately acting as an agent that enables long-term sustainable engagement. This duality is represented by the roman God Janus, which had two faces and thus representing this duality metaphorically.

pCommunity-driven strategies for transformative change in environmental protection

While we are basing our analysis at a conceptual level on the “enablers” concept from the Janus model, we also acknowledge that the model bases its evidence on drivers for these “enablers” to get involved in a seemingly top-down nature. This is reflected in the fact that there is a central actor that drives the involvement of other actors by identifying needs, and that central actor is typically an academic or scientific institution. In this paper, we acknowledge that the drivers for these relationships can stem from other sources, such as the willingness to get involved in environmental protection topics, and other intrinsic values of the Fab Lab movement, such as involvement with the (local) community, a collaborative mindset and openness. This reasoning is aligned with pleas “to support different types of citizen science and to offer support in the conceptualisation and design of emerging new forms of (citizen) engagement” and “to provide enough creative space where grassroots initiatives can flourish side-by-side with more established forms of scientific knowledge production” (Schäfer & Kieslinger, 2016). In the discussion section, we will argue that various Fab Labs around the world are becoming the de facto platforms where “the community can meet and exchange ideas so as to establish fertile grounds for [...] collaboration between citizens and scientists” (Schäfer & Kieslinger, 2016), since they can take on various roles (i.e. trainers, manufacturers, developers, community engagement), and that this phenomenon is worth observing and discussing, to find ways to promote it for further adoption.

Multifaceted roles of Fab Labs

As an ultimate goal, this paper aims to be a first step towards building upon the sharing and collaboration principles that Fab Labs advocate for, and leverage those practices in projects related to environmental protection. The Fab Charter (CBA, 2012), describes Fab Labs as “a global network of local labs, enabling invention by providing access to tools for digital fabrication,” as an infrastructure to “share an evolving inventory of core capabilities to make (almost) anything, allowing people and projects to be shared.” This global network has a proven capacity for collaborative educational endeavors through the worldwide distributed courses of Fab Academy, Fabricademy and Bio Academy and also their involvement at both the local and global level for the initiatives such as the FabXEvents, Fab Research, Fab City Global Initiative, the Resilience Collective, Fab Economy and Fab House (*The Fab Foundation*, n.d.).

In the online environment, the global network showcases its collaborative approach through the Fab Foundation Forum, which facilitates communication, knowledge sharing and collaboration between regional networks, and the fablabs.io platform (the online social network of the international Fab Lab Community) which provides a map with all the official nodes around the world, guidelines, machine information and other resources open accessible to the global community (Fab Labs Online Resources | FabLabs, n.d.).

Central to Fab Labs is a participatory way of working, which, arises due to its connections to three characteristics that creates a common narrative around the maker culture including “a strong emphasis on learning through hands-on creation, a transdisciplinary approach due to the different backgrounds of the people involved, and a strong ethos that knowledge should be freely accessible” (O’Duinn, F. (2012) as cited in Ferdinand et al. (2016)).

In this sense, Fab Labs are not only spaces equipped with digital fabrication tools but are collaborative platforms that support values of “collaboration, decentralization, participation, and the democratization of knowledge” (Gershenfeld, 2008). In the following paragraphs, we describe the diverse roles that Fab Labs have played in recent years, to later use these as a basis for better understanding the relationships and activities that are central to the analysis we carry out in this paper:

As learning spaces: empowering creativity and skill development

Fab Labs provide a platform for skill development and capacity building across a wide range of areas, including digital design, fabrication techniques, programming, electronics, and entrepreneurship. Furthermore, Fab Labs are also instrumental in supporting STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) while prioritizing the philosophy of “learning by doing,” encouraging users to engage in

hands-on activities, design challenges and projects, where they can apply theoretical knowledge in a practical setting.

As manufacturing spaces: from prototyping to testing and refining

Fab labs are equipped with both cutting-edge technologies such as 3D printers, laser cutters, CNC machines and traditional hands-on tools for production. This equipment can be used to develop innovative solutions such as custom sensors, data collection devices and prototypes for new (environmental monitoring) technologies. They can provide an ideal environment for rapid prototyping and experimentation, allowing for the testing and refining of new ideas and technologies before implementing them on a larger scale.

As service providers: enabling on-demand, fast prototyping solutions

Fab Labs can provide access to equipment and technology for the development of customized solutions. Through rapid prototyping tools, products and services can be quickly developed, tested and refined without the need for large-scale manufacturing resources.

As collaboration spaces: fostering interdisciplinary innovation

Fab Labs often attract a diverse group of people with various skills, including designers, engineers, biologists, data and social scientists, artists and undergraduate students. This interdisciplinary expertise can lead to creative and effective collaborations that might not emerge in a more homogenous environment. In terms of open innovation and inclusivity, Fab Labs typically operate on principles of open access, making their resources and facilities available to learners of all ages and skill levels.

As an ecosystem facilitator: community hubs for 'glocal' engagement

Fab Labs facilitate community engagement around a diverse range of topics by organizing training courses, workshops, hackathons, events, seminars and collaborative projects that are open for public participation. They can operate locally, engaging with representatives from various sectors within their cities, while also being integral to the global Fab Lab Network, which includes approximately 2,500 centers across 125 countries (How MIT's Fab Labs Scaled Around the World, 2023). This "glocal" approach enables them to maintain local relevance while benefiting from the visibility and collaborative opportunities provided by the international network.

Leveraging Fab Labs approaches in participatory processes and environmental action

Based on this background, this article focuses on an initial understanding on how environmentally aware communities and environmentalism practices (including approaches such as citizen science initiatives) and Fab Labs can combine efforts for addressing environmental action in various forms. Either by evidencing the potential for developing and accumulating community skills, or increasing the ability of sharing and exchanging data across different platforms, the study aims to further understand these relationships within this context. To do so, we conduct our analysis in an inductive manner, based on a set of preliminary observations, which then evolved into a deeper analysis by conducting semi-structured interviews, as explained in the methodology section.

In the following sections, we will show how Fab Labs and environmentally-focused citizen science activities, while distinct in formats and purposes, have converged into a common space, driven by shared values. As we will see in the following sections, this convergence has brought Fab Labs to fields beyond technology (i.e. not just data collection, or materials processing), and these collaborations have evolved into more complex relationships and activities over time.

2 Method

In order to substantiate our hypothesis about Fab Labs as “enablers” for environmental protection in multi-stakeholder initiatives, we have collected data in two different ways: through a literature review and semi-structured interviews.

2.1 Literature review and desk research

Initially, a literature review and desk research was conducted, aiming to identify existing cases in which Fab Labs were connected to participatory approaches on environmental issues. The desk research aimed to cover a selection of cases which could provide information about the activities, such as geographic location, the stakeholders participating in and impacted by the activities, the specific environmental issue addressed, the financial drivers of the projects, their connection with citizen science (if any), as well as the outcomes and achievements.

Identifying comprehensive documentation for the initiatives proved challenging, as many of the projects had already concluded or lacked accessible information. The lack of data highlighted the limitations of relying solely on desk research for a deep understanding of Fab Lab initiatives connected to environmental action. However, this desk research provided leads that could be further explored in more direct conversations. Consequently, we decided to conduct online (semi-structured) interviews with representatives of active and established initiatives identified through the initial research. As we will discuss in the following section, we acknowledge the limitation that this presents, as the contact points we could reach out to were primarily from the Fab Lab Network, which could present a biased perception of these relationships and activities.

2.2 Interviews

A strategy for conducting semi-structured online interviews was selected in order to gather up-to-date information and gain deeper insights into the initiatives’ past or current activities. The support of the Fab Lab Network was instrumental in this phase, as its well-structured and accessible community facilitated connections with key actors involved in the initiatives. As mentioned above, as positive as the Fab Lab Network connections are, the only interviewees we could interact with were stakeholders from the Fab Labs themselves. Although this choice was intentional, we acknowledge that additional information and interviews with other stakeholders would better substantiate the interviews, but due to various reasons such as time limitations, and some privacy concerns, the interviews were limited to Fab Lab members. This limitation in our study runs the risk of resulting in opinions and facts which are biased. To overcome this limitation, we provide additional resources such as news articles, documentation or other materials that can support the stories collected in these interviews. To effectively showcase how Fab Labs are contributing to environmental action, the following criteria have been refined to ensure a comprehensive selection of cases:

- **Geographical distribution:** In order to examine the environmental challenges specific to different regions, Fab Labs were selected from different countries across three continents, aimed at understanding regional variations and trends in the interaction between Fab Labs’ focus areas and environmental action.
- **Labs scale:** The selection included Fab Labs of varying scales, ranging from small, community-based labs to large institutions with significant public funding. This diversity allowed for an exploration of how resource availability and organizational scale influence the effectiveness and scope of local environmental initiatives.
- **Focus areas in research:** The analysis covered a broad spectrum of Fab Labs’ environmental efforts, including both urban and rural contexts.
- **Socio economic contexts:** The interviews incorporated Fab Labs operating in both low-income and high-income regions. This aspect aimed to identify how socioeconomic factors shape the approaches and impacts of environmental projects within different economic contexts.
- **Financing model:** The selection of Fab Labs or organizations was also based on their diverse funding structures, including publicly funded, privately funded and mixed-source labs.

The interviews followed a common template, which is included in the annex. The interviews took place via videoconference between June and July of 2024. Each session lasted approximately between 60 and 90 minutes and were carried out in parallel by the three authors of this paper.

2.3 Data analysis

After the interviews, the collected data was analyzed focusing on several key aspects to understand the role of Fab Labs in contributing to collaborative environmental action cases; this was done by establishing cross-connections between the different initiatives considering the similarities and differences in their approaches. Special attention was given to understand how Fab Labs engaged in collaboration with external organizations to implement their local projects, examining their specific roles as well as the drivers and barriers that influenced multi-stakeholder collaboration. The contextual factors, such as existing skills, location and their socio-economic scenarios were also key factors considered for a detailed understanding of the impact and effectiveness of the selected action.

3 Results

3.1 Citizen & Community-Led Actions for environmental protection: fab labs' stories

In this section, we present the results and insights from the desk research and the online interviews. First, the results of the desk research are presented in a table, including basic information on the projects and initiatives, as well as links to the online resources where this information was found. It is important to highlight that this desk research was complemented following the interviews, and that the additional information collected from those conversations is not included here. Below we show the most relevant results identified during this research (cf. Table 1).

Table 1: Desk research results

Title	Location	Topic/ Issue	Stakeholders involved	Period	Reference
Making Sense: Mapping noise in one of Barcelona's noisiest neighborhoods	Barcelona	Noise Pollution	Citizens, local communities	2015 -2017	(Woods et al., 2018)
Making Sense: Exploring digital and analogue sensors to create feeders using bird-centered design	Barcelona	Education on environmental topics	Students aged 9-14 years old	2015 - 2017	(Woods et al., 2018)
Making Sense: Empowering young people to investigate air pollution in Kosovo and power evidence-based campaigns.	Prishtina, Kosovo	Air pollution	Activists, young citizens	2015 - 2017	(Woods et al., 2018)
Making Sense: Tackling the most polluted streets in Amsterdam	Amsterdam	Air pollution	Data scientists, citizens	2015 - 2017	(Woods et al., 2018)
Hollandse Luchten	Amsterdam	Air pollution	Citizens, residents, business community, local government, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment	2018 - 2024	(Hollandse Luchten, n.d.)
Flowing Futures	Barcelona	Water quality assessment; Filtering processes; Micro-cultivation	Master students, local communities	2023	(Flowing Futures – Fab Lab Barcelona Research, Education, Innovation Centre, 2023)
Powar Steam	Barcelona	Food; Climate Change	Designers, local communities, teachers, students	2022 - ongoing	(POWAR STEAM, n.d.)
Open Farmer Kit	Milan	Environmental parameters; Biodiversity monitoring	Designers, students, local communities	2023	(Open Farmer Kit - Distributed Design Platform, 2024)
3ee	Milan	Monitoring of pollinator species	Designers, students, universities staff	2023	(3EE - Distributed Design Platform, 2024)
A multispecies design approach to a public space intervention	Greece	Biodiversity; Climate Change; Ecosystem preservation	Residents, local communities, university students	2023	(A Multispecies Design Approach to a Public Space Intervention - Distributed Design Platform, 2024)
Harbor Paris	Paris	Water conservation; Circular Economy; Heritage	Citizens, Local communities, students	2024 - ongoing	(HOME HARBORS EU, n.d.)
The Flip Flopi	Kenya	End of single use plastic; Circular Economy; Ocean Conservation; Heritage	Local communities, craftspeople, makers, recyclers, activists	2022 - ongoing	(The Flipflop, 2024)

Next, we present the results of the semi structured interviews by first providing a summary of the interviews conducted (cf. Table 2). A total of 9 interviews were conducted, out of the 11 different contact points that were contacted. All the interviewed Fab Labs contacts were from different nationalities, covering Europe, Africa and South America. Additional participants in Central Europe (The Netherlands and France) and Southeast Asia (Singapore) were approached, but our contact points were unable to respond before the submission of this paper. A relevant case to highlight which was not interviewed for this study, is the Waag Futurelab in Amsterdam (The Netherlands), which, due to time constraints, did not take part in this work, although its activities are highly relevant to this paper and will be part of future interviews.

The most relevant insights for each of the cases were extracted and presented in the following tables. (cf. Tables 3 to 11). A template was prepared identifying the most relevant information to be presented in this paper, assuming that not all data collected could be transcribed into those tables. In addition, we have added references to external resources for the projects and initiatives that the interviewees mentioned during the interviews, as a means of providing additional sources of information and checks on the information provided.

Table 2: Overview of environmental action initiatives developed by fab labs worldwide

Project	Country	Organization	Description of the project	Related environmental topics
The Floating FAB LAB Amazon	Peru	Fab Lab Peru	Floating platforms on the Amazon River and its tributaries acting as laboratories to facilitate access to technological tools to local communities. By providing training and technology, underserved communities will be able to develop initiatives that support biodiversity conservation while exploring solutions for a global regenerative economy. The laboratory emphasizes biotechnology, biomaterials, digital craftsmanship, entrepreneurship and forest conservation, with construction and component development executed through a distributed approach supported by a network of fab labs. The project concept was formally introduced in 2013 during the FAB9 in Yokohama, Japan. While the project is still in its conceptual phase, many activities and collaborations have been established focusing on disseminating the objectives and finding the financial resources for its execution.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water conservation - Biodiversity conservation - Deforestation prevention - Climate action - Restoration - Sustainable materials - Circular economy
Various. Most relevant is the Coastal Community of Vestmannaeyjar and Puffing Patrol	Iceland	Fab Lab Vestmannaeyjar	The Fab Lab is involved in various projects, including art-science exhibitions for promotion of biodiversity promotion (Sound of the sea (Merlin, n.d.)), citizen science initiatives for biodiversity protection (Puffin Patrol (Katz, 2024)), biodiversity monitoring by prototyping tracking devices for birdlife, and educational activities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity conservation - Food security - Preserving natural ecosystems
“Le guide des pratiques écologiques dans les labs” and AgroEcology programme	France	RFFLabs (interviewed AgriLab)	This guide highlights the active involvement of the members from RFFLabs in environmental aspects. Although the guide is not an environmental project in itself, the RFFLabs members collate their actions, events or developments in tutorials so that their experiences serve learning-by-doing makers, students and the general public. This collection of shared knowledge is aimed to change mentalities, sensitivities, ways of appropriating the tools, raise awareness on environmental issues; show how to grasp and develop these techniques and projects, propose other points of view, and other ways of acting for the common good. In terms of AgroEcology, AgriLab works on training at various levels, from university students to farmers. They promote ecological practices in agriculture and work on projects such as public dissemination of the role of pollinators.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Air pollution - Plastic recycling - Climate action - Energy security - Food security - Materials recycling
Fab City Challenge	Estonia ¹	Fab City Foundation	The Fab City Challenge is a collaborative innovation initiative designed to address social, environmental, and economic issues, known as ‘Challenges,’ on a local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water conservation - Waste management

¹ The Fab City Foundation was established as a legal and organizational structure in Estonia; however, it does not maintain a physical space in the country and operates its activities distributedly across different continents.

Project	Country	Organization	Description of the project	Related environmental topics
			scale. The program encompasses critical areas of intervention, where global teams collaborate with local initiatives to conceptualize and prototype design solutions. Three editions were already organized including Bali (Indonesia), Thimphu (Bhutan), and Yucatán (México).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Food security - Regenerative materials - Sustainable mobility - Preserving natural ecosystems - Climate adaptation agriculture
Making Sense	Spain, The Netherlands, Kosovo	Fab Lab Barcelona, Waag Society, Science for Change Kosovo	Making Sense was a project that aimed to explore how open source software, open source hardware, digital maker practices and open design can be effectively used by local communities to fabricate their own sensing tools, make sense of their environments and address pressing environmental problems in air, water, soil and sound pollution. Fab Lab Barcelona and the Waag Society in Amsterdam were two Fab Labs in this project, which was funded by the European Union as part of the H2020 programme. This project led to the consolidation of air quality monitoring tools on both Fab Labs, such as the Smart Citizen Project (Smart Citizen, n.d), and similar hardware developments in Waag. In addition, this project allowed the creation of methodologies in collaboration with academic partners, such as the Citizen Sensing Toolkit (Woods et al., 2018).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Air and noise Pollution
Couronne verte	Congo	Union Fab Lab	The project, launched by the French embassy in Congo, in collaboration with various stakeholders including Union Fab Lab and the local associations and foreign universities, works to promote plastic reduction and recycling, by advocating for better national regulations on the matter. The program includes training to young adults in plastic recycling, machines use, and creation of 3D printed filament from those items, and organizes training for more than 30 students per year.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plastic pollution - Materials recycling
ReMakeRS 2024: Emergency Design Challenge 2024	Brazil	Fab Lab Unisinos	The project is an Emergency Design Challenge that invites designers, makers, architects, carpenters, and other creatives to develop low-cost, easily replicable furniture for families affected by the floods in Rio Grande do Sul. Heavy rains, exacerbated by climate change, caused widespread flooding in the southern Brazilian state in late April and early May 2024, leaving hundreds of towns underwater. The designs follow an open-source model and are available for free to anyone or any company interested in producing, financing production, and helping the flood victims.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate action - Restoration - Sustainable materials - Circular economy
Sun Factory	Portugal	Fab Lab Benfica	The initiative aims to build a practical and accessible set of tools for solar-powered plastic recycling, specifically designed to address the needs of regions with insufficient or unstable electricity supply. It combines low-tech and high-tech components, produced in a makerspace. The Sun Factory setup provides	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zero Pollution - Water conservations - Plastic recycling - Materials recycling

Project	Country	Organization	Description of the project	Related environmental topics
			tools for shredding, melting, and injection molding wasted plastic materials into new products. The initiative connects with various local stakeholders to address water pollution and general plastic waste management issues. Additionally, it raises awareness and empowers citizens to reflect on their single-use plastic consumption and contribute to tackling plastic pollution.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preserving natural ecosystems
Tzoumakers community makerspace	Greece	P2P Lab Tzoumakers	Tzoumakers is an open lab established by P2P Lab in the rural area of Ioannina, Greece, in 2018. This makerspace has been closely developed with local community members, who cooperatively design and manufacture tools for small-scale agricultural production and govern the space. Tzoumakers operates on a commons model, where resources are shared and managed collectively. The initiatives and focus of work are driven by the community and the surrounding ecosystem. The main activities relate to energy security, through developing open-source windmills, and regenerative farming that involves low-tech solutions to support farmers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preserving natural ecosystems - Climate adaptation agriculture - Energy security - Sustainable materials - Circular economy

Table 3: Description of Fab Lab Peru related Initiatives

Organization		Fab Lab Peru	Topics	Water conservation; Biodiversity conservation; Deforestation prevention; Climate action; Restoration; Sustainable materials, Circular economy
			Duration / Status	+10 years / on-going
Initiative: The Floating FAB LAB Amazon	Stakeholders types involved	Fab Lab Network, NGOs, Foundations, Local government, Business & Industry (private and state-owned), Universities, Local communities	Evolution of the collaborations	<p>International cooperation with NGOs, Universities, Foundations, business and industries: Through global collaboration to support the construction and operational success of the laboratory, through grants, equipment and support of experts.</p> <p>Local government: Partnerships with local authorities' have been started considering their involvement in ensuring safety and regulatory compliance of the floating lab.</p> <p>Fab Lab network: The network has been supporting mapping of resources to be used as technological innovation, educational content and resources for community participation.</p> <p>*A key factor in the project's dissemination and visibility has been the support from FabLAT, the Latin American network of Fab Labs, founded by Fab Lab Peru. With close to 400 members across the region, FabLAT has been playing a vital role in broadening the project's exposure and fostering regional engagement.</p>
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Promote the initiative, seek allies, and coordinate operations.		
	Drivers	Public-private cooperation; Initiatives working at the intersection of technology and Amazonian biodiversity conservation		
	Barriers	Political instability; Lack of enthusiasm from key governmental actors over time; Corruption; Illegal activities accompanied by threats		
	Motivation	<p>Improve innovation lab infrastructure in the Amazon territory; Provide training for Amazonian youth, focusing on entrepreneurial mothers, children, and young people; Engage in biodiversity conservation efforts; Develop an alternative green economy through the integration of local, natural, and cultural knowledge, incorporating technological components.</p> <p>*International recognition has been a significant motivation for sustaining the project. For example, in 2015, the Floating FAB Lab Amazon was selected as one of the top 13 proposals from 800 to 1,000 submissions at the UN Sustainable Development Summit in New York, where the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were launched.</p>		

Table 4: Description of Fab Lab Unisinos related Initiatives

Organization		Fab Lab Unisinos	Topics	Climate action; Restoration; Sustainable materials; Circular economy
			Duration / Status	5 months / on-going
Initiative: ReMakeRS 2024: Emergency Design Challenge 2024	Stakeholders types involved	Fab Lab Network; Universities & students; Industry; Professionals (architects, designers, engineers, traditional carpenters, creatives); Local Government; Local communities	Evolution of the collaborations	<p>Fab Lab network: Initially launched as a single design workshop, the initiative rapidly grew across the country and beyond, thanks to the strong connection of the Fab Lab network who support with dissemination, connections to other actors and curation of the programme;</p> <p>Universities: Without having a proper funding, the initiative relied on volunteers staff and students to develop the ‘Challenge’ digital infrastructures, such as design graphics, website and social media;</p> <p>Professionals: Architects, designers, engineers, and makers contributed as juries for selecting the best cases in various categories and provided award options for the winners’ compensation.</p> <p>Local communities: The Fab Lab’s prior activities established a strong narrative and engaged local communities through efforts such as sheltering flood victims at the University, providing meals, serving as a donation hub, repairing electronics, and producing squeegees for cleaning affected houses.</p> <p>Industry: The initiative received donations from industry partners to build furniture for revitalizing day care centers affected by the floods.</p>
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Project coordination and management, providing structured methodologies to guide the project from inception to implementation; Fostering collaboration for engaging actors and networks to the action; Sharing its spaces for workshops and testing phases; Providing access to tools and machines.		
	Drivers	The news about the environmental and social consequences of the flooding deeply moved many people, prompting widespread support for the cause; The Fab Lab has a good connection with a diverse of actors in the region (both for public and private sector) that could support the initiative in different formats; Previous activities led by the Fab Lab helped to create a clear narrative and engagement.		
	Barriers	Time constraints to organize the initiative in a short time; Engaging the public focused on other urgent demands resulting from the disaster; Financial resources to develop the furniture during the implementation phase.		
	Motivation	Support people affected by the floods in the Rio Grande do Sul region by increasing visibility of its consequences and getting people engaged with the cause; Establish strong collaborations among nodes within the Fab Lab network; Foster collaborations between Fab Labs, other professionals, and industries promoting the use of new production methodologies.		

Table 5: Description of Fab City Foundation related Initiatives

Organization		Fab City Foundation	Topics	Water conservation and management; Food security; Regenerative materials; Sustainable mobility; Natural ecosystems preservation; Climate action
			Duration / Status	3 years / on-going
Initiative: Fab City Challenge	Stakeholders types involved	Local Fab Lab teams and makers; Citizens; Local communities; Local government; Depending on the challenges: Education institutes, healthcare institutes, traditional business, designers, activists, sociologists.	Evolution of the collaborations	<p>Local Fab Lab teams: A comprehensive workshop of approximately 8 weeks are carried out in the different challenges location to better understand the local context, including existing environmental issues, resources, practices, people, policies in place.</p> <p>Local communities: local communities support the mapping and co-designing of the challenges to ensure it is relevant to the local context.</p> <p>Local government: As members of the initiatives as a result of the agreement to the Fab City commitment the local municipalities normally support event implementation with logistics, access to venues, facilitating contacts and supporting the communication of the actions.</p>
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Global coordination of the challenges; Co-curation of the content in collaboration with the local team; Programme development; Documentation and impact assessment; Outreach and dissemination.		
	Drivers	Shared interests and common goals; Passion of people and citizens to make change; Communities well connected with environmental issues and their social impacts by day-to-day observations; Direct impact of the environmental issue on the participating communities.		
	Barriers	Language barriers and cultural differences in relation to community traditions require additional time and alignment to ensure local voices are considered and respected. Furthermore, securing funding can be a significant barrier in order to maintain resources and keep the initiatives running post-event.		
	Motivation	Supporting the mission of establishing methodologies and practical examples of the Fab City framework 'Products In Trash Out' (PITO) to 'Data In Data Out' (DIDO) in action by sharing knowledge globally while addressing problems locally. Promoting the idea of rethinking tourism behavior so that people leave behind a positive legacy and support local issues instead of creating a negative impact.		

Table 6: Description of Fab Lab Vestmannaeyjar related Initiatives

Organization		Fab Lab Vestmannaeyjar	Topics	Biodiversity conservation; Food security; Preserving natural ecosystems
			Duration / Status	+10 years / on-going
Initiative: Coastal Community of Vestmannaeyjar and Puffing Patrol (although plenty of others)	Stakeholders types involved	Local Nature Centers and Marine Research and Conservation Centers (Beluga Whale Sanctuary); Harbour Office; Local Museum; Fishing Industry; Local Authorities; Ministries of Education; Innovation and Industry	Evolution of the collaborations	<p>Local communities: Initial relationships started by proximity with local research institutions, and dynamic, proactive connections between the Fab Lab and other local stakeholders. Those relationships evolved in complexity, and involved more stakeholders as the partners developed trust, and results were satisfactory for both ends.</p> <p>Fab Labs network: Additional external network support through the Fab Lab network and the Distributed Design initiative brought in new expertise and activities, which expanded the range of activities that the Fab Lab could bring into the local context.</p>
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Provide resources for local actions such as events, exhibitions, training courses, art installations and projects in collaboration with various stakeholders, including the Nature Center and research institutions, and training for kids and young adults. Prototyping and small scale manufacturing.		
	Drivers	Connection with the local institutions and proactive activities in local environment		
	Barriers	Small Fab Lab with limitations in staff and difficulties to bring in new ideas to a small, sometimes “isolated”, community.		
	Motivation	Strong social connections within a close knit local community which is heavily involved in marine conservation. The island relationship with the marine environment is related to both, the biodiversity, and the fishing industry, an economic driver for the inhabitants. The community has a strong connection with the ocean, and the Fab Lab is aligned with that local context.		

Table 7: Description of RFFLabs related Initiatives

Organization		RFFLabs (interviewed AgriLab)	Topics	Air pollution; Plastic recycling; Climate action; Energy security; Food security; Materials recycling
			Duration / Status	+6 years / on-going
Initiative: Le guide des pratiques écologiques dans les labs	Stakeholders types involved	French Networks of Fab Labs (RFFLabs)	Evolution of the collaborations	The French Network of Fab Labs has been working together for several years, sharing practices among the Fab Labs. This shared platform was contacted by a private company that provided funding to create the guide, which allowed the Fab Labs to work
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Content writers.		
	Drivers	External request from private partner to create the guide.		
	Barriers	Coordination effort.		
	Motivation	Willingness to share knowledge and practices on ecology. Their approach shows there are alternatives to more traditional ways of doing, and their audience is engaged by the type of the fact that can work on hands-on projects.		

Table 8: Description of AgriLab related Initiatives

Organization		AgriLab	Topics	AgroEcology; Food security; Pollinators
			Duration / Status	6 years / on-going
Initiative: AgroEcology Programme	Stakeholders types involved	University; Agricultural Bank; Agricultural Federation.	Evolution of the collaborations	The Fab Lab is embedded in University La Salle, and was initiated for “creating the farm of the future”, and started a Fab Lab related to agriculture. It then evolved to provide a bridge between Fab Lab techniques and Agriculture, providing a focus on responsible practices, awareness, and a focus on ecology.
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Training and dissemination, provide access to machines and tools		
	Drivers	The Fab Lab is part of a University with Agriculture / AgroMachines and AgroEcology graduate programmes. Active community and curious people, people willing to learn and develop their business.		
	Barriers	Only highlighted the bureaucratic work and needs for reporting as being part of the University		
	Motivation	Being part of a larger university, the main motivation was to introduce different ways of working, and more “ecological practices”, rather than only “standard” ones. The interviewees expressed that reducing the impact of their agricultural practice, by means of working in AgroEcological terms, and disseminating the ways of working, was the main motivation, given the emergency in years ahead for climate change and food security.,		

Table 9: Description of Union Fab Lab related Initiatives

Organization		Union Fab Lab	Topics	Plastic pollution; Materials recycling
			Duration / Status	1 year / on-going
Initiative: Couronne verte	Stakeholders types involved	Foreign government embassy; Local NGO; Foreign University; European Union Delegation	Evolution of the collaborations	International cooperation with Universities and foreign government: Relationships were initiated by a call for proposals by Unverscience (Unverscience - Nous Connaître - Unverscience, n.d.). Union Fab Lab was selected for a project on plastic pollution, which allowed them to become in contact with the French Embassy and the local NGO Association Human Empress. The Fab Lab was selected on the basis that it would provide training and the space for 30 students per year to become ecology ambassadors, with two editions and growing numbers (30 applicants in the first year, +100 in the second).
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Engagement with the local community via training programs and events. The organization works on the training of ca. 30 “ecology ambassadors” per year on plastic recycling and the creation of 3D printing filament from the collected plastics. The organization provides a space for training, prototyping and works with other stakeholders to promote the adoption of plastic waste collection and recycling at a national level.		
	Drivers	Public-private cooperation; funding for the activities, purposeful training for local engagement		
	Barriers	No support from the local government, which makes the project depend on foreign sources for funding. Limitations on the impact they can achieve due to funding restrictions. Engagement with communities outside of Brazzaville is sometimes not welcome, in particular with indigenous communities.		
	Motivation	Willingness to be involved in activities for the community; work towards disseminating and reducing the impact of pollution on health and the ecosystems (to the extent of what’s possible locally); advocacy for policy improvement on plastic pollution		

Table 10: Description of Fab Lab Benfica related Initiatives

Organization		Fab Lab Benfica	Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Zero Pollution - Water conservations - Plastic recycling - Materials recycling
			Duration / Status	2 years / on-going
Initiative: Sun Factory	Stakeholders types involved	Universities & students; SME's; Industry; Professionals (makers, designers, engineers, creatives); Local Municipality; Local communities; Precious Plastic community members;	Evolution of the collaborations	The Sun Factory initiative was initially developed by an individual creative, drawing insights from the Precious Plastic Community. Fab Lab Benfica connected with the initiative at a local event, leading to a collaboration. Since then, Sun Factory has become part of Fab Lab Benfica's educational program, linked to the higher education school in three main ways: 1) As a project incubated within the Fab Lab. 2) As a theme for an open call encouraging creatives to utilize the methodology and tools for their own initiatives. 3) With the creative individual mentoring the younger generation of creatives.
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Promote the initiative, Providing access to tools and machines, Fostering collaboration for engaging actors, testing of practicability and iterating on design,		
	Drivers	Fab Lab is part of an educational institution and needs to provide the physical space and tools for making, funding for the activities, purposeful training for students, and connections to the neighborhood through interesting and meaningful activities.		
	Barriers	Bureaucracy of a public institution, little flexibility to adapt ad hoc - such as hiring supporting staff during moments of high workload, and lacking experts/dedicated personnel in areas like science communication. The capacity of students to learn both design and regenerative design simultaneously is challenging.		
	Motivation	Believing that design has the power to respond to the climate emergency and that digital fabrication is the tool to bring ideas into reality. Developing meaningful educational programs for students in which they can not only learn design and rapid prototyping methodologies but also put those methodologies into practice in a manner that addresses local challenges in the context of the climate emergency. Additionally, developing an innovative program to comply with the funding scope.		

Table 11: Description of P2P Lab related Initiatives

Organization		P2P Lab	Topics	Preserving natural ecosystems; Climate adaptation agriculture; Energy security; Sustainable materials; Circular economy
			Duration / Status	6 years / on-going
Initiative: Tzoumakers Community Makerspace	Stakeholders types involved	Fab Lab Network & makerspaces; Professionals (farmers, researchers, engineers, creatives); Local Government; Local communities; Universities, NGO's, Industry,	Evolution of the collaborations	P2P is based in the region, and they have been searching for a space to put their research on peer-to-peer and commons into practice for a while. Eventually, through collaboration with the municipality, they were able to establish the rural Tzoumakers makerspace. In the first phase, they mainly identified challenges around sustainable agriculture and climate adaptation. They began working directly with the surrounding farming community to prototype the first tools and machines. Over the years, the community around the space has grown, along with its needs. There has been a gradual shift towards finding practical solutions to local issues, such as achieving energy self-sufficiency.
	Role of the organization in the initiative	Promote the initiative; support the (building of commons based) governance model; support administrative aspects; fundraising and financial support; access to space, tools and methods		
	Drivers	Giving the community access to know-how: The local farming and wind energy community is active and willing to learn new methods and tools to apply in their context. Purposeful training of the local community highlights the potential of digital fabrication.		
	Barriers	Initially, establishing a sharing economy was challenging. There was a need to provide protocols for borrowing tools, access funding, and implement energy self-sufficiency holistically in the region. Administrative tasks included creating legal entities for the makerspace.		
	Motivation	Wanting to support the local region by addressing its challenges in a very practical and accessible manner. General belief in sharing design globally and producing almost anything locally, striving to make this idea a reality in the region. Their focus on environmental sustainability involves using local materials and production methods to minimize environmental impact, and they firmly oppose planned obsolescence. Design things to last. Are interested in putting a sharing economy into practice in the region - P2P is able to observe the change of mindset of local community members, which is inspiring to continue the work.		

4 Discussion

In this section, we discuss the main findings of our study based on the results collected, and we share additional reflections based on the research process we followed. First, we focus on the nature of the activities and relationships that took place in the various cases analyzed, and discuss the role of the Fab Lab as an “enabler” for those processes. Secondly, we focus on the main drivers, limitations and factors for their involvement, with highlights from various cases. Next, we discuss the temporal dimensions and how the relationships evolved; we attempt to categorize their different approaches in order to better understand how to promote these types of relationships among future collaborations, and to provide guidance in their adoption. Finally, although seemingly a secondary finding, we discuss the difficulties faced in finding collated information about activities related to environmental concerns where Fab Labs played a role; a finding which is paradoxical, since the Fab Lab Network advocates for shared resources and documentation.

Evolution of the collaborations

In the results section above we showed that the Fab Labs interviewed in this study generally developed relationships with local stakeholders in order to work on environmental related topics. In other words, for the cases studied, the activities that the Fab Labs were involved in were always in partnership with other institutions, in their majority in the local context, such as research centers, universities, NGOs, associations and, although to a limited extent, government authorities. In most cases, the interviewees expressed that their main motivation to get involved in these activities was to collaborate and support environmental protection efforts, and in the majority of the cases, those were already taking place, or being planned, by other local, and sometimes foreign, stakeholders. In general, the activities that the Fab Labs carried out in these initiatives involved developing connections with the general public and local communities, and in various cases educational and training aspects were a key factor for the involvement of the Fab Lab in the initiative. In general, this role could be seen as that of an “enabler” for either reaching the general public or more targeted groups (young adults, children, etc.) to spark involvement in these activities; in particular for the training case, it additionally provided rewards in the form of improved abilities and skills to those that participate, as well as the possibility to belong to an active group that works for a greater cause (i.e. protecting the environment). In the majority of the cases, it could be argued that the presence of the Fab Lab in the group enhanced the overall capacity to work collaboratively and engage with local communities as a result of the participatory profile that these spaces contribute to the collective skillset.

We also showed that the presence of the Fab Lab in these local networks can not be reduced to any single category, and that doing so would be detrimental to their involvement and potential support. The fact that the Fab Labs combine non-traditional training programs with digital manufacturing and prototyping technologies, makes their role in these initiatives multifaceted, in that they can present themselves as stakeholders with expertise that spans, to varying degrees, educational, community, or fabrication spaces, and that their capacity to develop all these roles in a flexible manner, makes them adaptive to the local needs.

4.1 Core drivers, obstacles and overall motivations

After reviewing our results, it became clear that the variety of contexts and cases is reflected in possible core drivers, obstacles and motivations. Beyond the drivers of fostering collaborations for environmental protection activities, several common factors were identified through the interviews as contributing to the involvement of Fab Labs in these initiatives. Public-private partnerships were noted as important mechanisms to leverage existing resources, efforts and funding, especially when initiatives managed to align with local government urban agendas. In this collaborative context, the presence of other technology or socially driven projects acting on environmental protection, such as those focused on using technologies to enhance biodiversity monitoring and sustainable practices, also provided an enabling scenario for the achievement of specific goals.

The benefits of strong regional connections with diverse actors across both public and private sectors can be interpreted as a result of the Fab Labs' legacies of previously successful activities and established engagement strategies. These connections enabled Fab Labs to, for example, tap into the shared interests and common goals of local communities where, depending on the case, motivation to get involved in environmental protection activities was triggered by daily observations and firsthand experiences with environmental challenges.

In exploring the obstacles faced by the interviewed Fab Labs, a range of factors has been identified that impact the effectiveness and long-term economic sustainability of the initiatives they take part in. These factors include limited financial resources, insufficient knowledge of environmental policy contexts, and other critical issues that hinder progress, such as political instability or shifts in governmental priorities. Insufficient funding emerged as a major obstacle for the majority of the Fab Labs, often leading to the restriction of scope and scalability of projects. Additionally, a lack of understanding of legislation and policy mechanisms was perceived as a limitation by the Fab Labs, making it more difficult to act on projects related to environmental protection and implement initiatives effectively. However, this factor could be considered as a pointer for the abovementioned multi-stakeholder relationships to identify the correct partners in those groups, which we have seen is the natural way for these activities to take place. In any case, there is a clear need for Fab Labs to better understand how to align their projects with existing policy frameworks and to liaise with experts in the field to overcome these obstacles. Another significant challenge identified in various cases was political instability; frequent changes create an uncertain environment, posing challenges in terms of economic sustainability due to lack of consistent support and funding over the long-term. Interviewees noted a tendency among local governments to prioritize short-term gains over long-term sustainability, probably as the result of four-year election cycles, which can influence the development and implementation of strategies needed to address complex challenges. This was particularly relevant in the case of Fab Lab Peru, where the initial enthusiasm of certain ministers for the Floating Fab Lab Amazon project decreased over time due to other governmental priorities.

An important insight from the interviews was the observed lack of alignment among government departments in their public agendas. This can be seen in examples where initiatives were conceived with multifaceted roles, such as in Peru, which aims to address environmental protection while also acting on challenges within education, research and community empowerment through entrepreneurship. The extensive and integrated scope was probably a limitation for the commitment of specific government departments, in addition to the allocation of financial support, since secretaries work with independent strategies and budgets. Lastly, complex cases such as the collaboration based in the Amazonian territories faced numerous obstacles to implement actions due to the existence of illegal activities such as logging and mining, and posed significant risks, including threats and abuses against those working to protect the environment and local communities. Finally, the case in the Republic of the Congo highlighted the support from foreign governments, while local governmental support was fundamentally lacking.

In addition to core drivers and obstacles, interviewees were asked about their primary motivations for getting involved in and sustaining projects related to environmental protection. The analysis revealed that personal motivations were stronger in the cases where communities were closely connected and acutely aware of their dependency on natural ecosystems. This was particularly evident in places like the Amazon rainforest in Peru, the Congo Basin or in the Vestmannaeyjar island in Iceland, where communities rely directly on natural resources for their economy, food production and transportation. Despite differences in case contexts, a willingness to produce locally, by using accessible local materials and production methods, as well as sharing knowledge globally through interconnected networks, proved to be a strong core value among the Fab Labs. This can also be seen in the cases of Portugal, Estonia and Greece, where different strategies ranged from local training to international gatherings to prototyping collaborative interventions. Another motivation identified by analyzing the cases was a focus on developing environmentally-related educational programs in which digital fabrication and traditional production methods, the latter as a way to preserve heritage practices, both played a central role as tools to bring innovative ideas into reality.

4.2 Temporal dimensions

Following on from the previous sections, we consider it relevant to explore the temporal dimensions of the relationships seen in our case studies, and to analyze their growth and impact over time. Except for the disaster response case in Brazil, the majority of the cases started with small activities that progressively evolved into more complex, interconnected action. As seen in the results section, various cases have worked alongside these initiatives for more than 5 years, which makes them particularly relevant to consider given long-term commitment obstacles in citizen engagement cases (Liñan, 2022). In cases such as Fab Lab Vestmannaeyjar, these relationships happened dynamically, due to local proximity and close knit relationships on the island, which followed the path described above towards more impactful activities, such as *The coastal community of Vestmannaeyjar*; in other cases, such as Fab Lab Peru, many iterations, workshops and related activities have taken place in collaboration with NGOs, industrial partners and education institutes since the project was launched in 2013.

We consider this temporal factor to be of special relevance, as it provides guidance for those seeking to foster and explore these types of collaborations with Fab Labs. For this purpose, we consider the concept of “spiral development” to be especially appropriate for describing these relationships; the concept is a term used within the Fab Lab Network that represents the iterative nature of technical prototypes in the form of a *spiral* that grows in size (complexity) as, simpler, cumulative steps (inner loops of the spiral) are secured and completed. In particular, we metaphorically use this term in order to describe how these relationships can evolve over time by taking small steps that help develop trust among stakeholders and consolidate the involvement of different parties. Each loop of the spiral is a step in that relationship, materialized by an action. When these loops are unrolled over time, the leap between each step (loop) is the increased trust that ideally allows the collaborating parties to perform more complex actions and activities collectively (cf. Figure 1).

Figure 1: Evolution of relationships and Spiral Development Visualization

An additional outcome of these leaps is their potential to increase impact on target groups, environmental indicators and outcomes. These outcomes are beyond discussion in this study, as they require further analysis and are more complex in nature. However, we consider the “spiral development” concept to be relevant in combination with stakeholder mapping and resources assessment tools, so that expectations can be managed for the outcomes of actions taken. In other words, a framework of this kind can be applicable to provide qualitative indicators to assess what the expected outcomes and impact can be, by assessing the temporal dimension in forms of maturity of the relationships, while also providing a pathway to take “small leaps” towards more advanced outcomes. In addition, a special case is considered for those single actions that take place in short periods of time, which, to achieve impactful outcomes, require

significant levels of expertise and resources, such as the *ReMakeRS 2024* disaster response to the floods in the Rio Grande do Sul region in Brazil. In other words, either by contextual needs (the occurrence of a disaster), or other factors, if impactful short-term actions are sought, there is a need for the careful orchestration of various stakeholders with significant levels of expertise, and, in the particular case of the Fab Labs, the leveraging of the (Fab Lab) Network capabilities.

4.3 Thoughts on the findability of documented cases

In this last paragraph, we would like to highlight the difficulty in finding collated information about the activities that Fab Labs are taking part in within the field of environmentally related activities, be it monitoring, protection, advocacy or any other. While this paper has aimed to provide an initial assessment of a relatively low number of Fab Labs, it shows that there is great potential for future work on the topic. However, the lack of collated information and resources, as well as the inexistence of a global forum for sharing practices, experiences and guidance, is at the same time paradoxical and interesting to explore. This presents a unique opportunity for Fab Labs to coordinate efforts by leveraging already existing ways of working and sharing, with potentially little effort in setting up the infrastructure for these conversations to happen.

5 Conclusion

5.1 Fab Labs as enablers for engagement in environmental protection

In this paper, we showed how various Fab Labs are involved in environmentally related activities, a field that does not necessarily pertain to their originally envisioned role. We also detailed how Fab Labs are developing relationships with local communities and different kinds of stakeholders: universities, research centers, associations, NGOs and government authorities, and how Fab Labs are becoming “enablers” for environmentally related initiatives and activities. With this paper, we have attempted to understand how the “enabler” role comes about, and we have seen that various Fab Labs around the world are building relationships by leveraging their core activities (i.e training, prototyping, and small scale manufacturing) as well as the values that they advocate for: openness to the community, knowledge sharing and collaborative and proactive mindsets. We have seen how these characteristics make Fab Labs suitable for facilitating connections among various stakeholders. We have also shown the main drivers, motivations and obstacles for Fab Labs, identifying key factors that foster or hinder their involvement, and highlighting the importance of identifying key stakeholders that can overcome obstacles related to certain fields of expertise, such as policy and environmental law.

In addition, we have seen that a key characteristic is for these relationships to evolve and become more complex over time, and we have attempted to provide some theoretical tools for understanding and assessing collaborative relationships, as well as how to manage expectations around the impact that the actions these groups take on can achieve. Finally, we have shown how this multifaceted approach has fostered long-term collaborations and synergies between the stakeholders involved, a factor of special importance in participatory processes.

Fab Labs and environmental initiatives, while distinct in formats and purposes, are deeply interconnected through their shared commitment to democratizing knowledge and fostering community-driven action. Regardless of the specific role a Fab Lab plays in these ecosystems, they offer a hands-on and collaborative space that can support environmentalists’ needs. We believe that environmental initiatives and communities would benefit from the type of practices that already take place in Fab Labs as well as their willingness to be involved in activities alongside the community. While we consider this paper a first attempt to collate these activities in a systematic way, there is great potential to further observe and analyze these relationships, and to find ways to promote these collaborations in order to achieve greater impact.

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Annex - Semi-structured interview template

Project details

References: HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01 | Project N° 101133983

Project Starting date: 1 January 2024

Project End date: 31 December 2027

Background

Date:

Name of the interviewee:

General information:	
Official name of the organization:	
Location:	
Starting year and period of implementation:	
Number of employees/ collaborators:	
Website:	
Fablabs.io link:	
SoMe:	
Brief description of the initiative:	

Operations and structure	
<i>What are the main services provided by the fab lab/ organization in general?</i>	
<i>Does the fab lab/ organization have defined strategic areas of work? (Or what are the main topics the organization focus on?)</i>	
<i>What is the financing model of the organization? Is it public, private, public-private?</i>	
<i>Which profiles of organizations/ people does the fab lab/ organization normally work with?</i>	

Environmental-related initiatives information	
<p>Have your fab lab/ organization been involved in projects, actions or initiatives related to environmental protection or citizen science? Give more details.</p>	
<p>In what specific environmental topics or issues is/ was your fab lab/ organization connected?</p>	
<p>Are you aware if there was any policy mechanism/ regulation/ law in place connected to the topic?</p>	
<p>What was the duration of the initiative?</p>	
<p>Was it financed? How?</p>	
<p>What was the role of the organization (or asking at a personal level to the interviewee) in this project or initiative?</p>	
<p>What were the main stakeholders (and collaborators) of the initiative? How did those relations come about?</p>	

Community engagement strategies and impact	
<p>What were the main achievements/outcomes/outputs of the project?</p>	
<p>What was the main target involved in the action/ initiative/ project</p>	
<p>What about the main drivers for active engagement and participation?</p>	
<p>Which have been the most effective tools and arrangements and why?</p>	

<p><i>How and to what extent has this initiative improved collaboration, co-creation and ownership by different actors? Has it contributed to specific and measurable outputs and outcomes?</i></p>	
<p><i>What were the main barriers and difficulties encountered?</i></p>	
<p><i>Does (did) your Fab Lab measure the impact or effectiveness of your contributions? How?</i></p>	

<p>Motivation and future</p>	
<p><i>What was the main motivation for developing the project/ initiative?</i></p>	
<p><i>Is the organization planning or willing to initiate another project/ initiative related to environmental action?</i></p>	
<p><i>What resources or support would be helpful for further developing and expanding your Fab Lab's involvement in citizen science and environmental initiatives</i></p>	
<p><i>Are you interested in sharing and exchanging further information on environmental related topics with an NGO/ more4nature project?</i></p>	